

Effect of Compaction and Leaching on Heat of Transport of Soil Water

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Manuscript received 6 January 1986, revised 17 December 1986, accepted 6 July 1987

Thermal diffusion of water in an alluvial soil at various degrees of compaction and in a saline soil, subjected to various degrees of leaching, has been studied. The heat of transport was calculated by using a relation based on irreversible thermodynamics. The results are interpreted in terms of the nature of interactions of the diffusing soil-water with the neighbouring soil particles.

THERE have been reports of some studies on thermal diffusion of water in soils and clays¹⁻⁷. A fairly recent review in this line has also appeared⁸. The heat of transport of water which emerges from such experiments is known to be sensitive to the nature of interactions inherent in the system under consideration, and is thus considered useful in providing an index of soil-moisture interactions^{9,10}. The present paper describes such experiments on alluvial and saline soils with an attempt to correlate the resultant heat of transport of soil water ($\hat{Q}_w$) with the degree of soil compaction and leaching.

Experimental

The soils used were an alluvial soil collected from district Nadia and a saline soil from 24-Parganas (Canning) with textures of sandy loam and silty loam, respectively. Organic carbon, pH, C.E.C., E.C. of (1:2) soil extract, clay content and water holding capacity (by weight) of the two soils were 0.63%, 6.1, 9.7 meq/100 g, 0.6 Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹, 16.6%, 51%, and 0.74%, 8.0, 11.2 meq/100 g, 4.2 Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹, 20.6% and 68.8%, respectively. A detailed description of the diffusion cell has been given elsewhere⁷. It consisted of three chambers made of perspex and was properly insulated. The soil sample was placed in the middle chamber sandwiched between the two terminal water chambers.

The alluvial soil was compacted to bulk densities of 0.875, 1.02, and 1.31 g cm⁻³ in the central chamber and maintained at 70% degree of saturation for conducting the thermal diffusion runs. The saline soil was leached to E.C. values of 2.1, 1.2 and 0.5 Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹ before the actual diffusion runs. The heat of transport was also determined in the original saline soil (E.C.=4.2 Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹). The degree of saturation was maintained at 70% for the original and the leached saline soil samples.

The heat of transport of water ($\hat{Q}_w$) in the soil was calculated by using the following relation, based on non-equilibrium thermodynamics,

$$\hat{Q}_w = -\bar{V}_w T (\Delta P / \Delta T)_{st}$$

where, $\bar{V}_w$ is the molar volume of water, T is the mean (absolute) temperature and $(\Delta P / \Delta T)_{st}$ refers to the steady state value across the soil chamber. The measurements were made in triplicate.

Results and Discussion

The values of average heat of transport of water ($\hat{Q}_w$) along with the statistical analysis have been presented in Tables 1 and 2. The positive values of $\hat{Q}_w$ correspond to an absorption of heat behind and a liberation ahead of the diffusing soil water⁹. There was a decrease in $\hat{Q}_w$ value in the alluvial soil at higher levels of bulk density from 0.875 to 1.31 g cm⁻³ (Table 1). This may possibly be due to a concomitant decrease in the net area of contact of soil particles with water. A rise in $\hat{Q}_w$ with progressive leaching of salts (predominantly chlorides) from the saline soil (Table 2) is also consistent with the disruptive effect of chloride on the structure of water⁹.

On plotting the $\hat{Q}_w$ values against the electrical conductivity of (1:2) soil extract of the original as well as the leached saline samples, a linear correlation was obtained (Fig. 1). If electrical conductivity of the soil can be assumed to be zero, the value of $\hat{Q}_w$ would be 1.975 J mol⁻¹ (Fig. 1). The latter would represent the inherent $\hat{Q}_w$ for the given soil devoid of salts. The salts thus contribute 0.255 J mol⁻¹ towards the given $\hat{Q}_w$ (Table 2).

TABLE 1—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF WATER IN ALLUVIAL SOIL (SANDY LOAM) AT VARIOUS BULK DENSITIES

Observation no.	Mean Temp. (T) K	ΔT K	$\bar{V}_w$ ml mol ⁻¹	Bulk density of soil g cm ⁻³	$\Delta P=(h_H - h_C)^*$ cm	$\hat{Q}_w$ J mol ⁻¹
1.	306.6 (±0.40)	3.0 (±0.35)	—	0.875	-11.9 (±0.40)	2.17 (±0.202)
2.	306.4 (±0.35)	3.1 (±0.31)	18.098	1.02	-10.2 (±0.30)	1.81 (±0.122)
3.	306.4 (±0.17)	3.0 (±0.12)	—	1.31	-9.0 (±0.41)	1.61 (±0.087)

* Differential thermal expansion of water in the water chambers has been considered.

TABLE 2—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF WATER IN SALINE SOIL (SILTY LOAM) AT VARIOUS DEGREES OF LEACHING

Observation no.	Mean Temp. (T) K	ΔT K	$\bar{V}_w$ ml mol ⁻¹	Electrical conductivity (1:2) Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹	$\Delta P=(h_H - h_C)^*$ cm	$\hat{Q}_w$ J mol ⁻¹
1.	305.5 (±0.23)	5.1 (±0.61)	—	4.2	-15.9 (±0.30)	1.72 (±0.182)
2.	305.4 (±0.36)	5.0 (±0.38)	18.092	2.1	-17.2 (±0.25)	1.85 (±0.174)
3.	305.5 (±0.49)	5.0 (±0.38)	—	1.2	-17.8 (±0.25)	1.92 (±0.168)
4.	305.4 (±0.72)	5.0 (±0.36)	—	0.5	-18.1 (±0.35)	1.97 (±0.160)

* Differential thermal expansion of water in the water chambers has been considered.

Fig. 1

References

1. S. A. TAYLOR and J. W. CARY, *Trans. Int. Con. Soil Sci.*, 1960, 1, 80.
2. J. W. CARY and S. A. TAYLOR, *Soil Sci Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1962, 26, 413, 417.
3. J. W. CARY and S. A. TAYLOR, *Soil Sci Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1964, 28, 167.
4. R. P. TRIPATHI and B. P. GHILDYAL, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1978, 26, 313.
5. S. K. SANYAL, B. G. MAITRA and M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1983, 31, 464.
6. A. K. MUKHERJEE and S. K. SANYAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 761.
7. S. K. SANYAL and S. BANDYOPADHYAY, *Indian Agric.*, 1985, 29, 159.
8. R. C. SRIVASTAVA and RAJ PAL, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics in Soil Physics", Oxford-IBH, New Delhi, 1978.
9. J. N. AGAR, *Adv. Electrochem. Electrochem. Eng.*, 1983, 3, 31.
10. S. K. SANYAL and M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 1071.